

DEALING WITH CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES DURING COVID 19: UNDERSTANDING PARENTAL PERSPECTIVES

^aSariya Shabnam

^bFarha Hossain

^{ab}University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh

^asariya.shabnam.ierdu@gmail.com

^bfarha972119@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Parents of children with disabilities often appear to experience considerable stress and weakened emotional-well being. It is likely that the anxiety and emotional state of the parents are further exaggerated due to disrupted schedules of their children with disabilities during COVID 19 pandemic because of long-term school closure. The study aims to understand parental perspectives of dealing with children with disabilities during COVID 19 pandemic with an emphasis on the parent-child bonding. Fifteen parents and caregivers of children with disabilities participated in this qualitative study through semi-structured telephonic interviews. They were asked questions about behavioural changes of their children as well as bonding between themselves during this pandemic. Interview data were transcribed verbatim and thematic analysis technique was performed through manual coding. The findings of this study reveal that, significant behavioural changes of children with disabilities including increased restlessness, anger, fear, stress, hyper-activity, unwillingness to participate in academic as well as daily living activities, lack of motivation and concentration, significant learning loss, increased tendency of self-harming have occurred during covid-19 outbreak. The parent-child bonding seems to be highly affected (e.g. decreased quality time span & loss of parental patience during joint attention) by children's behavioural changes occurred due to school closure. Overall, the study finds that the emotional wellbeing of parents of children with disabilities and their bonding with their children have been unfavourably impacted by COVID19 pandemic. The study recommends that access to therapeutic services to support children with special needs can minimize the adverse effect of this lockdown. In addition, provision of expert wellbeing support for parents is also recommended.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemic, Bonding, Parents, Affect, Behavioural Change, Perspective.

1. Introduction

Human lives are threatened by the breakout of the novel Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). As of 29th April 2021, COVID-19 has affected more than 140 million individuals across 184 countries (World Health Organization, 2021). In Bangladesh, the first case of COVID-19 was identified by IEDCR on 8 March, 2020 (Dhaka Tribune, 2020). The government of Bangladesh announced school closure from 18 March, 2020 to prevent the transmission of coronavirus (MoE, 2020). A total of 700 Thousands people are infected by this devastating virus as of 29 April, 2021 in Bangladesh (DGHS, 2021). This new COVID infection is pronounced to be a worldwide pandemic by the World Health Organization (Bandyopadhyay, 2020). As COVID-19 pandemic keeps on extending in Bangladesh and in the world, the

current flare-up isn't just affecting wellbeing and monetary circumstances yet additionally on mental prosperity of people (Unicef, 2020). The everyday lives of families and children have likewise been changed, as numerous nations have shut schools, parks, and child-care facilities (Chung, Lanier, & Wong, 2020). In the current setting of lockdown and limitation of movements, children have compelled admittance to socialization, play and physical contact which are basics for their psychosocial wellbeing and advancement (Unicef, 2020). School terminations are keeping youngsters from admittance to learning and restricting their collaborations with peers which is causing anxiety in them (Imran, Zeshan, & Pervaiz, 2020). Coronavirus is additionally bringing new stressors on parents and guardians which can hamper their ability to give sufficient care and stay engaged and co-operative with their child, specially for those who have children with special needs, these challenges are exacerbated (Cluver, Lachman, Sherr, Wessels, Krug, Rakotomalala...McDonald,2020). However, according to Unicef (2020), across Europe and Central Asia, children with disabilities are profoundly helpless against shame, separation and isolation from the remainder of society. Also, presently, with the Coronavirus pandemic, they face much more serious dangers of rejection, neediness and an absence of admittance to urgent crucial services (Unicef, 2020). This study attempts to reflect behavioural changes of children with disabilities due to COVID-19 pandemic that may strongly affect parent-child relationships.

2. Literature Review

Parents dealing with children with disabilities face significant difficulties related to their physical, financial, emotional, psychological well-being as well as family and social life (Nimbalkar, Raithatha, Shah & Panchal, 2014). Children with disabilities require more attention as well as time from parents, which can increase parental stress (Algood, Harris & Hong, 2013). Children with Intellectual Disability and Autism Spectrum Disorder are more likely to experience increased stress, depression and anxiety (Cooke, Smith, & Brenner, 2020; Mutluer, Doenyas & Aslan Genc, 2020; van Steensel & Heeman, 2017). Parents of children with disabilities seem to obtain a lower score in terms of Quality of Life (QOL) that is significantly correlated with their children's functional independence (Leung & Li-Tsang, 2003). The current COVID-19 context has disrupted life in every corner of the world and will likely disproportionately affect those children with pre-existing vulnerabilities (Unicef, 2020).

School closure, social distancing and home confinement may have adverse effects on children with and without disabilities (UNESCO, 2020). Moreover, research shows that the parental stress and emotional well being of parents of children with disabilities had been ominously affected by Coronavirus pandemic (Alhuzimi, 2021). Parental unemployment, financial crisis, low level of social support, mismatch between the demands of parenting and resources available to meet those demands may cause parental burnout that leads to child abuse and negligence (Griffith, 2020). Obligatory home confinement due to COVID-19 raises the time period to be spent with the child. Parents with children with disabilities are likely to develop more stress and depression during COVID-19 pandemic (Dhiman, Reed, Ganesh, Goyal, & Jain, 2020) and may face increased demands in terms of supporting their child (Tolan, 2020). Depression among parents and caregivers is strongly correlated with employment status (Nam & Park, 2017). Literature shows that parents of children with disabilities face a higher proportion of losing jobs and children's increased inaccessibility to learning materials and healthcare support since the emergence of COVID pandemic compared to those without disabilities (Save the Children, 2020). Parental stress directly affects parent-child relationship closeness (Chung et al., 2020 ; Russell, Hutchison, Tambling, Tomkunas & Horton, 2020).

Children with disabilities are considered as a high-risk population and most vulnerable to COVID-19 pandemic (Gabrielli & Lund, 2020; Wong, Ming, Maslow & Gifford, 2020). The outbreak seems to have long-term impact on the development of children with disabilities (Neece, McIntyre & Fenning, 2020). Some literature focused on the challenges faced by the families of children with disabilities due to the pandemic (Mbazzi, Nalugya, Kawesa, Nimusiima, King, van Hove & Seeley, 2021; Neece et al., 2020). Focus on the advocacy, collaboration and necessary support service has been given through a number of researches conducted in Italy, Spain, China, UK, Saudi Arabia and other countries (Navas, Amor, Crespo, Wolowiec & Verdugo, 2021; Frederick, Raabe, Rogers & Pizzica, 2020; Goh, Lim, Foo, Ong, Aishworiya, Nair,.....Sung, 2020; Samadi, Bakhshalizadeh-Moradi, Khandani, Foladgar, Poursaid-Mohammad & McConkey, 2020; Toseeb, Asbury, Code, Fox,& Deniz, 2020; Toquero, 2020). According to previous research parents as well as caregivers are left alone not just in dealing with their children's home-tutoring yet in addition to dealing with their children and the home environment all in all. During the isolated interaction, the day to day environments of the families have changed abruptly and significantly. In the home environment, the instructive part and educational role of guardians for children has gotten a lot more significant than previously (Uzun, Karaca, & Metin, 2021).

Teaching children with disabilities at home addresses an alternate test to instructing neurotypical children. The effect of home education is probably going to be felt especially distinctly by the guardians of children with disabilities who were abruptly needed to address their children's issues throughout the day and consistently, without the usual support (Toseeb et al., 2020). Several research focused on E-inclusion, home education and distant learning for children with disabilities (Aarnos, 2021; Nusser, 2021; Parmigiani, Benigno, Giusto, Silvaggio & Sperandio, 2020). The outbreak of the Coronavirus pandemic toward the start of 2020 constrained a large number of school understudies to change from face to face instruction to distance learning (Aarnos, 2021). Although there exists a few studies on parent-child interaction and attachment (Uzun. S, 2020), limited qualitative studies are found regarding the behavioral changes and bonding between children with disabilities and their caregivers during Covid-19 pandemic.

Bangladesh is home to an immense number of individuals with disabilities – albeit tragically there is no particular information showing the specific number. The 2016 Household Income and Expenditure Survey showed that almost 6.94 percent of the populace was composed of individuals with disabilities (in excess of 11 million individuals), however the World Health Organization assesses that it is probably going to be more like 15%. As per the Situation Analysis on Children with Disabilities (2014), children with disabilities in Bangladesh are clearly among the most marginalized while referred to schooling (Unicef, 2020). There are various sorts of instructive arrangements in Bangladesh for children with disabilities. These incorporate for the most part; special education, integrated education, mainstream education. Other than these arrangements, home based education is to a great extent seen when other alternatives are not open. Home-Schooling is fundamentally relying upon guardians and relatives to give training to their children at home (Campe, 2011). As Bangladesh has a centralized education system, with the announcement of school closure from the government all the educational institutions were closed including schools for the children with disabilities.

3. Objectives

This study investigates parental perspectives of dealing with children with disabilities during COVID-19 pandemic with an emphasis on the parent-child bonding. This study attempts to answer to the following research questions:

- (i) What type of behavioral changes have occurred in children with disabilities during COVID-19 pandemic according to their parents?
- (ii) How COVID-19 period affect the bonding between the parents/caregivers and their children with disabilities?

4. Methodology

A combination of purposive and maximal variation sampling was performed to conduct this qualitative study. Data was collected from 15 parents and caregivers of children with disabilities until the data saturation took place. Each parent gave informed consent to participate in this study. Having at least one child with disability was the inclusion criteria of purposive sampling. Authors tried to address different types of disabilities (e.g. Physical Disability, Intellectual Disability, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Hearing Impairment, Visual Impairment, Down Syndrome and Multiple Disability) through maximal variation sampling. Semi-structured telephonic interviews were taken to conduct in-depth interviews and collect data from the participants. They were asked questions about behavioral changes of their children as well as bonding between themselves during this pandemic. It took approximately 15-20 minutes to complete each interview. Interview data were transcribed verbatim and cross-checked with the audio tapes to avoid mis-information and exclusion of any relevant data.

Thematic analysis was performed manually to analyze the data through the following steps: (i) Familiarizing and transcription of verbal data, (ii) generating initial codes, (iii) searching for themes, (iv) theme reviewing, (v) defining and naming themes and (vi) producing the report(Braun & Clarke, 2006). Authors coded the data individually, then cross-checked as well as resolved the issues through discussion. Participants's socio-demographic data were descriptively analyzed by the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

4.1 Socio-demographic Profile of the Participants

Participants' sociodemographic data including parents and caregivers' gender, age, community, occupation, children's age and types of disability are presented through Table 1.

Table 1: Sociodemographic data

Variables	n(15)	%
Gender		
Male	2	13.3
Female	13	86.7
Age (year)		
20-25	1	6.7
25-30	3	20.0

	30-35	1	6.7
	35-40	7	46.7
	40-45	2	13.3
	45-50	1	6.7
Community			
	Urban	9	60
	Rural	6	40
Occupation			
	Businessman	2	13.3
	Day Laborer	1	6.7
	Housewife	8	53.3
	Service Holder	1	6.7
	Tailor	1	6.7
	Teacher	2	13.3
Children's Age (year)			
	5-10	3	20.0
	10-15	11	73.3
	15-20	1	6.7
Children's Type of Disability			
	ADHD	1	6.7
	Autism (ASD)	3	20.0
	Down Syndrome	2	13.3
	Hearing Impairment (HI)	2	13.3
	Intellectual Disability (ID)	2	13.3
	Multiple Disability (MD)	1	6.7
	Physical Disability (PD)	2	13.3
	Visual Impairment (VI)	2	12.3

5. Results

A total of 15 in-depth interviews were taken for this study. Among them only 13.3% are male, the rest 86.7% participants are female. 60% of the study participants were living in urban areas, whereas 40% of them were living in rural areas. Most of the participants were housewives (53.3%). Other participants were involved in different occupations like business (13.3%), teaching (13.3%), tailoring (6.7%) and day labour (6.7%). Childrens' types of disability included ADHD (6.7%), Autism Spectrum Disorder (20%), Down Syndrome (13.3%), Hearing Impairment (13.3%), Intellectual Disability (13.3%), Multiple Disability (6.7%), Physical Disability (13.3%) and Visual Impairment (13.3%).

5.1 Theme-01: Behavioral Changes of Children with Disabilities due to COVID-19 Pandemic

A total 15 respondents provided their opinion regarding behavioral changes of the children with disabilities during the pandemic. Transcribed data of the participants were categorized into some sub-themes.

Increased restlessness : Majority of the participants (9/15) reported that their children have developed increased restlessness as well as inconsistency and anxiety. Parents reported inaccessibility to all kinds of therapies and interventions, changes in routine, suffocation due to home confinement to be main reasons for this behavioral change. One of the interviewee stated that:

She liked school very much. School closure made changes in her routine. She couldn't accept this. Everyday she takes her bag and wants to go to school at her school time. When we tell her that we can't go to school, she starts crying and shows restlessness. (Respondent 10)

The condition seems to be more serious in children with Neurodevelopmental Disabilities like those with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Intellectual Disability (ID). Parent having a child with ADHD noted that:

As he is a child with ADHD, he has to take some exercise regularly from his school. We faced inaccessibility to all kinds of therapies and exercises due to Covid. So, we have no control over him. He is too restless and this has increased nowadays. He wants to go out but he is not willing to wear a mask. He throws it out. (Respondent 7)

Showing increased stress and fear : More than one-third of the study participants (6/15) noticed increased stress and fear in their children's behavior. According to the respondents, long term home confinement creates an additional pressure on their mental health which is expressed through these types of behaviors. One of the interviewees reported, going out of the house after so many days made her child very frightened and insecure. She stated that:

Whenever we take him outside nowadays, he starts screaming and gets scared. Maybe he gets frightened coming outside after so many days. (Respondent 3)

Moreover, inability to cope with the online classes as well as the new normal make children with sensory disabilities more stressed and fearful of the post-covid world. Parent of a child with Visual Disability said:

He stays home all the time and often shows stress about being unproductive for this long time. He gets disappointed at small things and as he is not that much expert in using technology, he is passing boring time, even cannot attend the online classes if he wants to which seems very depressing for him. (Respondent 11)

Significant learning loss : 6 out of 15 participants noted that their children are facing significant learning loss including socialization skills and ADL (Activities of Daily Living) due to this pandemic. According to the parents, lack of regular practice and monitoring make their children facing learning loss. Parent of a child with ASD noted that:

She learnt a lot from her school, but now she can't recall them. We notice significant learning loss. I can't make her regularly practice these types of activities as I can't give her enough time. I have a personal business. As you know this type of children depend solely on practice. If it is not continued regularly, the child may forget those. (Respondent 10)

Increased anger : 5 among 15 participants reported increased anger in their children with disabilities. They are showing tantrums as their families are not allowing them to go outside. One of the respondent reported that:

He wants to go outside as he feels some type of suffocation. But we don't allow him to do that. Then he shows anger and stops eating. (Respondent 1)

Less interest in performing academic and daily activities : Some respondents (4/15) opined that they notice a lack of interest in their children in terms of performing academic and daily activities. Parents reported that some schools have arranged online classes for their children, but these types of online classes don't work for them. Parent of a child with Hearing Impairment stated that:

He can't join online classes as he has problems in hearing. He is not willing to continue his study anymore. (Respondent 1)

Parents also reported that their children are troubling with lack of concentration and motivation which may refrain them from performing daily activities properly. Some parents also noticed increased laziness in their children due to school closure. One of the interviewee dealing with a child with Down Syndrome reported:

He has become very lazy compared to the days before covid. He was more active before. I have to force him to do his daily work.....Being lazy, he is becoming bulky. (Respondent 5)

Increased hyperactivity : A few respondents (2/15) reported their children's hyperactivity to be increased a lot more than before. Mother of a child with Intellectual Disability noted that:

Repetitions in unexpected behaviour also increased. He also disturbs his siblings more than before. If any guest comes to our house his problem arises more. He starts to disturb them also. (Respondent 13)

Increased tendency of self-harming : Only one respondent opined that her child's tendency to self-harm has increased in this pandemic period than before. She said:

.....often she hits herself. When she goes to school she shows these behavioural issues less. (Respondent 10)

5.2 Theme two: Bonding between Parents and their Children with Disabilities During COVID-19

The bonding between parents, caregivers and children with disabilities have taken a new dimension during COVID-19. The changes can be explained in several sub-themes.

5.2.1 Decreased Quality Time Span Leading to Weakening Bonding

4 out of 15 participants (almost one-third of the participants) reported that before the quarantine period, children and parents used to spend less time home, after working all day they used to spend fruitful time which was favourable for each other, but due to lockdown the scenario has changed. One parent stated that she faces mental pressure and stress when she thinks about her child. She further said:

I am often tense about my child. Bonding between my child and myself becomes stronger when I take my son outside to spend some time together. But in this situation it is impossible for me, so I get less quality time with my child which is creating chaos between us. (Respondent 3)

During this COVID-19 lockdown, violence was accounted for at a higher rate in families with parents/caregivers or children with disabilities furthermore, those families all the more often detailed boundaries to getting to abusive behavior at home and mental health services (Save the Children, 2020).

5.2.2 Decisive Impact to Some Extent for Spending Together (parent-child) Time

3 among 15 participants have found some positive consequences of lockdown. Due to home confinement, parents are spending more time with their children. One of the participant mentioned:

My child is now staying closer to me and I am able to teach her some household activities with the child's participation has increased than before (Respondent 14).

While interviewing a parent of an ASD child, she reported that:

Previously, we couldn't give him enough time. But now we spend more time with him. (Respondent 2)

Another parent of an ADHD child stated that:

Due to the lockdown, his father's office is closed so he can give enough time to our child. Previously, he was unaware about child's care, but now spending more time with my child has made him understand the issues.....Our child has improved in terms of eye contact. Our understanding has improved (Respondent 7).

Children are learning a lot of new activities in their stay home period too, one of our participants explained that she tries to keep her child busy in drawing, dancing etc and maintain a daily routine for the child (Respondent 9).

5.2.3 Loss of Parental Patience

Majority of the participants (7/15) talked about their suffocation and stress about their child. A mother who has a child with Down Syndrome stated:

Sometimes, I feel very upset with all these. I feel stressed and just wait to start our regular life like before. We had routines for both of us when everything was normal. Now it has all changed, that's what makes me feel suffocated. As my child doesn't want to perform his duties timely nowadays and shows laziness. (Respondent 5)

Moreover, one participant mentioned her increasing restlessness for dealing with her child all day which gives her trumpertantrum often and she is unable to control and later she shouts at her child.

I often get tired as I have 3 more children to deal with and he destroys things and disturbs his siblings. I must confess that I run after scolding him when I can't take it anymore. I threaten him with a stick in my hand that I'm going to scold him if he doesn't hear me. Then he gets afraid and calms down for some time. Then again starts it (Respondent 13).

A participant dealing with a child with ASD mentioned:

Before Lockdown when she went to school and spent 3-4 hours with her teachers, I at least had some time for myself. I used to feel relaxed and talk with my friends and companions. But in this lockdown period this is not possible. I have to look after her 24/7, deal with her restlessness and make her calm. It becomes difficult for me to control my tantrum (Respondent 10).

6. Discussion

In this study, we investigated the effect of the COVID-19 episode on guardians' and children's mental wellbeing, bonding, behavioral changes with specific reference to families of kids with disabilities. All the more explicitly, we researched parental viewpoints about their children's behavioural patterns and their interaction during and before the pandemic. Additionally, we investigated the reasons which drove changes in conduct and how they can be dealt with to limit the effect of home-restriction. Studies led on the pandemic pestilence have uncovered that the pandemic influences psychological wellness (Golberstein, Wen, and Miller, 2020).

The present study reveals that children with disabilities are confronting significant changes in terms of behavioral outcomes. Changes in routine, inability to adapt new strategies, physical isolation from peers, disintegration of support networks have profound behavioural consequences on children with disabilities (Asbury, Fox, Deniz, Code & Toseeb, 2020 ; Wong et al., 2020 ; Juneja & Gupta, 2020). The study found increased restlessness among children with disabilities according to their parents' perception. This goes consistent with previous study that revealed more aggression and typically regressive behaviour, misbehaviour and temper tantrums among children with disabilities during COVID pandemic (Imran, Zeshan & Pervaiz, 2020). This study addressed that more than one-third of the participants explained to notice increased stress and fear among their children with disabilities. Previous studies that found children with disabilities to be more likely to face acute anxiety, stress and fear during this pandemic support this finding (Asbury et al, 2020; Mutluer, Doenyas & Aslan Genc, 2020; Liu, Bao, Huang, Shi, & Lu, 2020). Lower understanding of the pandemic situation in minimal and non-verbal children is often expressed through stressed and troublesome behaviour (Asbury et al, 2020). Feeling of tremendous distress and worsened

mental health sometimes turns into self-harming activities (Theis, Campbell, De Leeuw, Owen, & Schenke, 2021), especially those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (Mutluer et al., 2020). In case of children with sensory impairments, inability to attend online classes like their peers causes an extra mental burden and distress, which is expressed through stressed behaviour. Another study in Malaysia which goes consistent with this finding reported that children with sensory impairment struggle with comprehending their lessons delivered through online classes as well as familiarity with online devices (Krishnan, Mello, Kok, Sabapathy, Munian....& Kanan, 2020). Home confinement due to school closure and stress resulting from the crisis may lead to difficulties in learning and cause learning regression (World Bank, 2020; Theis et al., 2021). This study points out significant learning loss among the children with disabilities due to inaccessibility to regular therapy and intervention services. Unwillingness to perform academic and daily activities due to lack of motivation and concentration is another finding of this study that supports the previous study that revealed lack of motivation in children with disabilities causes significant behavioural change which is hard for the parents to cope with (Asbury et al, 2020). In addition, we also found increased hyperactivity of the children with disabilities in this study. In support of this finding, Imran et al., 2020 and Mutluer et al., 2020 pointed out children with disabilities to form hypersensitivity and demand more attention from the parents and caregivers during this covid period.

As a subsequent advance, we researched the bonding among children and parents during the lockdown. We discovered a slump in quality time spending, decline in parental tolerance were the principal indicators of parental stress. Consequently, it appears to be that the connection among guardians and children are even more significant during the pandemic cycle. In this interaction, children need to spend all the time at home with their folks and kin until the pandemic finishes. The significant thing is to assist them with getting this interaction as sound people (Uzun et al.,2021). Concerning children's attachment with guardians (as perceived by the parents), we found that guardians revealed a significant loss of parental patience as their children seem not to listen to them often and they show increased levels of hyper-activity, stubbornness and anxiety. The result explored that, parents who have more children experience more trouble during this home quarantine. In support to this, Uzun et al., 2021 defines as parents are left alone at home not only taking care of their children's schooling, but also helping them to cope with the home environment, mothers who have only one child participate more in their children's activities and feel less burdened. Concerning parental stress, researchers tracked down that the Coronavirus pandemic and the connected exacting regulation estimates had a negative sway, autonomously of the children's demonstrative status. Truth be told, both the guardians of kids with and without disability, reported expanded parental pressure during the lockdown contrasted with previously (Bentenuto, Mazzoni, Giannotti, Venuti, & de Falco, 2021).

Furthermore, this study found that there are also definitive positive impacts of home confinement to some extent. By spending more time together, giving the parents and child opportunities to explore and understand each other better than before, their communication is improving. In research from Mbazzi et al (2021), it is also found that the first phase of this COVID-19 lockdown improved connections and comprehension in the families of children with disabilities, ensured more friendly practices among the children, saving practices and adequate time for family works. Children are getting oriented with new activities. Their active association is bringing positive consequences, their support in the family has expanded. Being a parent of children with disabilities is often stressful and parents need a lot of endurance, the lockdown has made this scenario even more tough. Parents seem to experience extended challenges just as an additional difficulty in endeavoring to fulfill the requirements to their parental job during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has been featured in previous research (Bentenuto et al., 2021).

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

To summarize, our qualitative outcomes uncovered an overall expansion in parental pressure and adverse consequences of the quarantine period on childrens' practices during home confinement. Moreover, our results show the importance of initiating support services as well as intercessions that straightforwardly include the guardians. The study recommends that access to therapeutic services to support children with special needs can minimize the adverse effect of this lockdown. In addition, provision of specialized wellbeing support for parents is also recommended. If parents try to be resourceful for their children with necessary knowledge and support, the quality of time spent can be increased which may positively impact the bonding between themselves and their children.

Notwithstanding a lot of the challenges that have emerged during the isolation period, we tracked down that a few guardians admired the chance to invest more energy on their child, passing more time and felt that this has fortified the parent-child relationship. Research also showed that support from both of the parents inside the family positively impacts the parent-child relationship during the isolated cycle (Uzun et al., 2020).

References

- Aarnos, R. (2021). *Teaching and supporting students with special-educational needs at distance during the COVID-19 school closures in Finland:special needs teachers' experiences.* (Unpublished master's thesis). Abo Akademi University, Tuomiokirkontori, Turku, Finland.
- Algood, C. L., Harris, C., & Hong, J. S. (2013). Parenting Success and Challenges for Families of Children with Disabilities: An Ecological Systems Analysis. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 23(2), 126–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2012.747408>.
- Alhuzimi, T. (2021). Stress and emotional wellbeing of parents due to change in routine for children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) at home during COVID-19 pandemic in Saudi Arabia. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 108, 103822. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2020.103822>.
- Asbury, K., Fox, L., Deniz, E., Code, A., & Toseeb, U. (2020). How is COVID-19 affecting the mental health of children with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities and their families? *PsyArXiv Preprints*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/sevyd>.
- Bandyopadhyay, S. (2020). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): we shall overcome. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 22(3), 545–546. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-020-01843-w>.
- Bentenuto, A., Mazzoni, N., Giannotti, M., Venuti, P., & de Falco, S. (2021). Psychological impact of Covid-19 pandemic in Italian families of children with neurodevelopmental disorders. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 109, 103840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2020.103840>.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.
- Bureau Of Statistics, Bangladesh (2016). Retrieved April 29, 2021, from <http://203.112.218.65:8008/WebTestApplication/userfiles/Image/LatestReports/HIES-10.pdf>.
- Campe (2011). The status of un-served children in education Children with Disability in Bangladesh. https://www.campebd.org/Files/16032014020857pmChildren_with_Disability_in_Bangladesh.pdf.
- Chung, G., Lanier, P., & Wong, P. Y. (2020). Mediating Effects of Parental Stress on Harsh Parenting and Parent-Child Relationship during Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic in Singapore. *Journal of Family Violence*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10896-020-00200-1>.
- Clarke, L. S., Embury, D. C., Jones, R. E., & Yssel, N. (2014). Supporting Students With Disabilities During School Crisis. *TEACHING Exceptional Children*, 46(6), 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040059914534616>.
- Cluver, L., Lachman, J. M., Sherr, L., Wessels, I., Krug, E., Rakotomalala, S., McDonald, K. (2020). Parenting in a time of COVID-19. *The Lancet*, 395(10231), e64. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30736-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30736-4).
- Cooke, E., Smith, V., & Brenner, M. (2020). Parents' experiences of accessing respite care

for children with Autism Spectrum disorder (ASD) at the acute and primary care interface: A systematic review. *BMC Pediatrics*, 20(1), 1–12.

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19). (2021, April 30). Retrieved April 30, 2021, from <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coron>.

COVID-19 (2020). Retrieved April 29, 2021, from <http://103.247.238.92/webportal/pages/covid19.php>.

Debnath, A. (2020, July). Disability and COVID-19 in Bangladesh: why urgent action is needed[Blog Post]. Retrieved from <https://www.sightsavers.org/blogs/2020/07/disability-covid-bangladesh-urgent-action-needed>.

Dhiman, S., Sahu, P. K., Reed, W. R., Ganesh, G. S., Goyal, R. K., & Jain, S. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 outbreak on mental health and perceived strain among caregivers tending children with special needs. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 107, 103790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2020.103790>.

Dhaka Tribune (2020, March 8). First 3 cases of coronavirus confirmed in Bangladesh. Retrieved from <https://www.dhakatribune.com>.

Frederick, J. K., Raabe, G. R., Rogers, V. R., & Pizzica, J. (2020b). Advocacy, Collaboration, and Intervention: A Model of Distance Special Education Support Services Amid COVID-19. *Behavior Analysis in Practice*, 13(4), 748–756. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40617-020-00476-1>.

Gabrielli, J., & Lund, E. (2020). Acute-on-chronic stress in the time of COVID-19: assessment considerations for vulnerable youth populations. *Pediatric Research*, 88(6), 829–831. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-020-1039-7>.

Goh, T. J., Lim, T., Foo, M., Ong, S. K. A., Aishworiya, R., Nair, T., Sung, M. (2020). Supporting individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder in medical settings during COVID-19. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 54, 102441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102441>.

Golberstein, E., Wen, H., & Miller, B. F. (2020). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) and Mental Health for Children and Adolescents. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 174(9), 819. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.1456>.

Griffith, A. K. (2020). Parental burnout and child maltreatment during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Family Violence*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10896-020-00172-2>.

Imran, N., Zeshan, M., & Pervaiz, Z. (2020). Mental health considerations for children & adolescents in COVID-19 Pandemic. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 36(COVID19-S4), S67–S72. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.36.COVID19-S4.2759>.

Juneja, M., & Gupta, A. (2020). Managing Children with Special Needs in COVID-19 Times. *Indian Pediatrics*, 57(10), 971. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-020-2009-1dhttps://doi.org/10.47405/mjssh.v5i8.472>.

Liu, J. J., Bao, Y., Huang, X., Shi, J., & Lu, L. (2020). Mental health considerations for children quarantined because of COVID-19. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4(5), 347–349. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-4642\(20\)30096-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-4642(20)30096-1).

- Mbazzi, F. B., Nalugya, R., Kawesa, E., Nimusiima, C., King, R., van Hove, G., & Seeley, J. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 measures on children with disabilities and their families in Uganda. *Disability & Society*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2020.1867075>.
- Ministry of Education, Bangladesh (2020). Retrieved April 30, 2021, from <http://www.moedu.gov.bd/site/news/e02fc350-7137-44c3-868a7ffa22cb280f/%E0%A7%A7%E0%A7%AE-%E0%A6%A5%E0%A7%87%E0%A6%95%E0%A7%87-%E0%A7%A9%E0%A7%A7-%E0%A6%AE%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%B0%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%9A-%E0%A6%AA%E0%A6%B0%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%AF%E0%A6%A8%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%A4-%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%95%E0%A6%B2-%E0%A6%B6%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%95%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%B7%E0%A6%B E-%E0%A6%AA%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%B0%E0%A6%A4%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%B 7%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%A0%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%A8-%E0%A6%AC%E0%A6%A8%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%A7-%E0%A6%98%E0%A7%8B%E0%A6%B7%E0%A6%A3%E0%A6%BE%E0%A5%A 4>.
- Mutluer, T., Doenyas, C., & Aslan Genc, H. (2020). Behavioral Implications of the Covid-19 Process for Autism Spectrum Disorder, and Individuals' Comprehension of and Reactions to the Pandemic Conditions. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 11, 561882. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.561882>.
- Navas, P., Amor, A. M., Crespo, M., Wolowiec, Z., & Verdugo, M. (2021). Supports for people with intellectual and developmental disabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic from their own perspective. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 108, 103813. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2020.103813>.
- Nimbalkar, S., Raithatha, S., Shah, R., & Panchal, D. A. (2014). A Qualitative Study of Psychosocial Problems among Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy Attending Two Tertiary Care Hospitals in Western India. *ISRN Family Medicine*, 2014, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/769619>.
- Nusser, L. (2021). Learning at home during COVID-19 school closures – How do German students with and without special educational needs manage? *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 36(1), 51–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2021.1872845>.
- Orsander, M., Mendoza, P., Burgess, M., and Arlini, S.M. (2020). The hidden impact of COVID-19 on children and families with disabilities. London, *Save the Children International*. <https://resourcecentre.savethechildren.net/library/hidden-impact-covid-19-children-global-research-series>.
- Parmigiani, D., Benigno, V., Giusto, M., Silvaggio, C., & Sperandio, S. (2020). E-inclusion: online special education in Italy during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Technology, Pedagogy and Education*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939x.2020.1856714>.
- Russell, B. S., Hutchison, M., Tambling, R., Tomkunas, A. J., & Horton, A. L. (2020). Initial Challenges of Caregiving During COVID-19: Caregiver Burden, Mental Health, and the Parent–Child Relationship. *Child Psychiatry & Human Development*, 51(5), 671–682. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10578-020-01037-x>.

- Samadi, S. A., Bakhshalizadeh-Moradi, S., Khandani, F., Foladgar, M., Poursaid-Mohammad, M., & McConkey, R. (2020). Using Hybrid Telepractice for Supporting Parents of Children with ASD during the COVID-19 Lockdown: A Feasibility Study in Iran. *Brain Sciences*, 10(11), 892. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci10110892>.
- Su-Jung, N., & Eun-Young, P. (2017): Relationship between caregiving burden and depression in caregivers of individuals with intellectual disabilities in Korea, *Journal of Mental Health*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2016.1276538>.
- Theis, N., Campbell, N., De Leeuw, J., Owen, M., & Schenke, K. C. (2021). The effects of COVID-19 restrictions on physical activity and mental health of children and young adults with physical and/or intellectual disabilities. *Disability and Health Journal*, 101064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dhjo.2021.101064>.
- Tolan, P. (2020). Commentary: Enabling efficient and full application of prevention strategies for population mental health reflections on Dodge. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 61(3),268–271.<https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.13196>.
- Toseeb, U., Asbury, K., Code, A., Fox, L., & Deniz, E. (2020). Supporting families with children with special educational needs and disabilities during COVID-19.<https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/tm69k>.
- Toquero, C. M. D. (2020). Inclusion of People with Disabilities amid COVID-19: Laws, Interventions, Recommendations. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 158. <https://doi.org/10.17583/remie.2020.5877>.
- UNESCO New Delhi (2020). Life in the Times of Covid-19: A Guide for Parents of Children with Disabilities. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/news/another-covid-19-front-line-parents-children-disabilities>.
- Unicef (2020). UNICEF Europe & Central Asia Region (ECARO). Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) Situation Report No. 1. <https://reliefweb.int/report/albania/unicef-europe-central-asia-region-ecaro-novel-coronavirus-covid-19-situation-report>.
- Unicef (2020). Psychosocial support for children during COVID-19 A manual for parents and caregivers.<https://www.unicef.org/india/reports/psychosocial-support-children-during-covid-19>.
- Unicef (2020). Greater inclusion for children with disabilities.*Most initiatives for children with disabilities are specialised and separate* <https://www.unicef.org/bangladesh/en/greater-inclusion-children-disabilities>.
- Uzun, H., Karaca, N. H., & Metin, E. (2021). Assessment of parent-child relationship in Covid-19 pandemic. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 120, 105748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105748>.
- Van Steensel, F. J. A., & Heeman, E. J. (2017). Anxiety Levels in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Meta-Analysis. *J Child Fam Stud*, 26(7), 1753-1767. doi:10.1007/s10826-017-0687-7.
- WHO Disability considerations during the COVID-19 outbreak. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/disabilityconsiderations-during-the-covid-19outbreak>.

- World Bank Group (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic: Shocks to Education and Policy Responses. <https://doi.org/10.1596/33696>.
- Wong, C. A., Ming, D., Maslow, G., & Gifford, E. J. (2020). Mitigating the Impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic Response on At-Risk Children. *Pediatrics*, *146*(1), e20200973. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2020-0973>.
- World Health Organisation (2021). COVID-19 Weekly Epidemiological Update. https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20210420_weekly_epi_update_36.pdf.
- Yuen Shan Leung, C., & Wai Ping Li-Tsang, C. (2003). Quality of Life of Parents who have Children With Disabilities. *Hong Kong Journal of Occupational Therapy*, *13*(1), 19–24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1569-1861\(09\)70019-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1569-1861(09)70019-1).